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Ethical Dilemmas when Promoting Critical Thinking in Higher Education

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Abstract

This article explores the imperative of fostering critical thinking in Higher Education, with a particular focus on literary studies. Grounded in the belief that thinking critically enhances students' capacity to perceive the world from diverse perspectives, it navigates through key principles shaping learning, teaching, and assessment. Besides, signature pedagogies in literary studies are depicted as platforms for knowledge creation and the development of critical thinking skills, emphasizing the subjective nature of certain contexts and the importance of perspective over a rigid dichotomy of right and wrong. The article then delves into learning theories, highlighting the significance of personalized, student-centered approaches that consider factors like motivation, context, and engagement. It advocates for a balanced integration of learning styles and multiple intelligences, challenging the conventional idea of a one-size-fits-all teaching style. The role of the teacher as a critically reflective practitioner is underscored, with small group activities and technology utilization highlighted as effective strategies for stimulating critical thinking. The importance of aligning assessment with learning outcomes, ensuring reliability, validity, and transparency, is also emphasized. The ethical dimension of teaching critical thinking is scrutinized, navigating the delicate balance between maximizing challenge and prioritizing students' well-being. Drawing on ethical dilemmas, the article suggests an ethics of care, urging teachers to engage in collaborative discussions, recognize multiple forces at play, and trust institutional structures. In conclusion, it advocates for a holistic approach to critical thinking, integrating principles, practices, and moral considerations. Likewise, it underscores the interconnectedness of teaching, learning, and critical thinking, calling attention to the need for an inclusive, reflective, and ethically informed educational environment.

Keywords: Critical Thinking, Higher Education, Ethical Dilemmas, Personalized Learning, Reflective Teaching

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1 Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of Higher Education, fostering critical thinking skills has become increasingly imperative, particularly in disciplines such as literary studies. This article delves into the multifaceted aspects of cultivating critical thinking among students, recognizing its pivotal role not only in academic pursuits but also in shaping individuals capability of navigating the complexities of the contemporary world. The overarching research problem addressed herein pertains to the effective integration of principles, practices, and ethical considerations in the pursuit of instilling critical thinking within the curriculum. The primary objective of this research is to examine and elucidate the key principles influencing learning, teaching, and assessment in Higher Education, emphasizing their interconnectedness in nurturing critical thinking. Furthermore, the article aims to explore the ethical dilemmas inherent in challenging students while prioritizing their well-being and to propose strategies for navigating these challenges effectively. To contextualize the research, a comprehensive review of relevant literature is undertaken. The exploration begins with an analysis of signature pedagogies in literary studies, highlighting the shift from information delivery to knowledge creation and critical thinking skills development. Drawing on prominent educational theories, the article navigates through the significance of personalized learning, cognitive apprenticeship, and the research-teaching nexus in enhancing this kind of thinking. Additionally, ethical considerations in teaching, particularly the balance between challenge and student well-being, are examined in light of existing literature on educational ethics.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to contribute nuanced insights into the intricate interplay of factors shaping critical thinking in Higher Education. By addressing the identified research problem, this article seeks to offer practical strategies for educators, administrators, and policymakers to optimize learning environments. Furthermore, the ethical dimension explored within the context of critical thinking underscores the broader societal impact of fostering individuals ability of thoughtful reflection and engagement. As we embark on this exploration, it becomes evident that unravelling the complexities of critical thinking necessitates an all-encompassing approach, weaving together pedagogical principles, instructional practices, and ethical considerations to cultivate a fertile ground for intellectual and personal growth.

2 Key Principles Influencing Learning, Teaching and Assessment in Higher Education

The successful combination of suitable learning activities and outcomes, effective teaching strategies, and positive assessment methods are crucial elements in the educational process. These elements play a substantial role in shaping the dynamics between teachers and students, influencing their expectations and objectives within the classroom. Consequently, the aim of this section is to explore, recognize, and evaluate key principles that impact the learning, teaching, and assessment

processes in Higher Education, fostering students' involvement in critical thinking practices. The divergence among learning perspectives arises from their focus on the essential elements that shape students' learning encounters. Several key learning theories revolve around four influential factors: the learner's interaction, the impact of the context, comprehension of the learning task, and active engagement in learning processes. First, learner-based theories center on students and adopt growth or developmental models. These theories view intelligence as dynamic, underscoring learners' motivations, needs, and drives. Second, context-based theories argue that external factors, such as students' relationships with their surroundings, exert a greater influence than internal aspects like students' motivations. Unlike learner-based theories, context-based approaches place the locus of learning beyond the individual. Third, knowledge-based theories focus on the activities students participate in and establish hierarchies of knowledge that vary based on societal and cultural values. Lastly, process-based theories critically assess experiences, enabling students to act based on these analyses. However, numerous factors impact learning processes and diverse methods exist for acquiring knowledge. Therefore, all theories hold value, as learning is a multifaceted activity with a broad spectrum of processes. Given the importance of teaching strategies for promoting critical thinking skills, it is more advantageous to integrate and apply multiple theories to gain a comprehensive understanding of these processes rather than pursuing a single theory that encompasses all possible scenarios [1].

As mentioned earlier, certain theories concentrate on the teaching context and the learning environment. A fundamental principle influencing learning is the creation and enhancement of suitable learning conditions aligned with the Higher Education curriculum and its pedagogies [2]. Concerning the curriculum, it is crucial that the level of demand is appropriate and tailored to students' needs, embraces diverse perspectives by presenting opposing views, and fosters integrity and originality. Regarding the pedagogies within the curriculum, it is important that their guidance promotes a sense of belonging among students through encouraging mutual engagement, respect, and generosity. Additionally, these pedagogies should not only stimulate students by cultivating a passion for learning but also instill confidence in their own abilities and potential. Another key principle involves transitioning from a focus on learning styles to acknowledging multiple intelligences [3]. The concept of learning styles, suggesting that students acquire knowledge in different ways, may be misleading as there is insufficient evidence supporting the incorporation of learning-style assessments in general educational practice. While some scholars reject the learning-styles hypothesis, they also do not advocate for a single teaching style. Similarly, other studies propose that the emphasis in education should be on methods that better develop students' abilities, such as critical thinking, considering that each individual learns in a unique manner [4].

The learning process then should be individualized as much as possible by incorporating various possibilities and choices. The classroom setting should create opportunities for students to collaborate, emphasizing cooperation over competition in a social and communal environment. Besides, the assessment methods should be diverse and varied [5]. Indeed, there is evidence suggesting that providing open

access to content enhances students' learning acquisition [6]. This approach allows students to showcase their abilities and knowledge in diverse ways [7], and teaching techniques should be adapted to the unique needs of each student [8]. Consequently, it is essential to examine the fundamental principles influencing the teaching process, and how this process interacts with and reinforces effective learning practices that encourage students to engage in thinking more critically.

Given the role of a teacher who reflects critically and possesses good intentions, along with the commitment to act responsibly and professionally, there is no assurance of achieving an effective teaching performance with students. To be more specific, external factors such as the complexities of social and political learning on one hand, and the intricacies of human relationships on the other, play a significant role in the teaching-learning process. Nonetheless, teachers can mitigate the impact of certain assumptions and practices on their performance by adopting a critically reflective approach [9]. By embracing this reflective perspective, teachers should collaborate with students to create opportunities for mutual knowledge development instead of relying solely on information delivery. Likewise, emphasizing the importance of students' perspectives enhances their ability to cultivate individual thinking, fostering an environment where each student is valued, heard, and encouraged to engage in critical conversations. Engaging in activities within small groups and incorporating technological resources are two effective strategies that positively impact the previously mentioned teaching approach. These strategies can be implemented and seamlessly integrated into the seminar-style teaching format [10]. Seminars create an environment conducive to discussions, where teaching, learning, and critical thinking unfold simultaneously. As a result, seminars facilitate teacher-student interaction, allowing them to explore diverse perspectives and expand their understanding of ambiguity and complexity. Similarly, seminars offer an ideal platform for fostering cooperative learning practices between teachers and students. For instance, through posing open-ended questions, teachers can initiate an inclusive and critically constructive discussion where each student actively participates and interacts with others. To achieve this, seminar leaders need to be well-prepared and have a clear comprehension of the seminar's objectives and anticipated outcomes.

Assessment stands as another crucial element in the educational setting necessary for cultivating students' critical thinking abilities. Some studies posit that assessment should be considered an integral part of the learning process, breaking it down into three phases. First, learning outcomes need to be selected and defined. Second, assessment tasks should be crafted in alignment with the predetermined outcomes. Third, these assignments should be connected to the relevant learning activities students undertake throughout the module [11]. Additionally, these studies emphasize the incorporation of three principles into the assessment process. The first principle is "reliability," or the expectation that consistent outcomes will be achieved in the end [12]. The second is "validity," which determines if the assessment is suitable for the given task. And the third is "transparency," which encompasses feedback and feedforward to inform students of expectations. Likewise, assessment should be regarded as an inherent aspect of the learning-teaching process to avoid a disconnect between assessment, learning, and teaching [13]. In other words, as-

assessment should be characterized as a series of nuanced curriculum practices that involve and influence students and faculty in their teaching and learning practices in order to create alternative modes of addressing it.

Expanding on the earlier notion that there might not be definitive right or wrong responses in reflecting on literary texts and engaging in critical thinking about them, it is essential to address the debate around formative assessment being labeled as "good" and summative assessment as "bad" [14]. Contrary to this dichotomy, all forms of assessment should cohesively contribute in Higher Education, and rather than being seen as conflicting, to consider them inherently complementary. Moreover, students should take an active role in customizing their own educational experience by making choices of their own. Consequently, assessment should be seamlessly incorporated into the

3 Key Challenge: To Engage in Critical Thinking

After exploring key theories influencing the dimensions of learning, teaching, and assessment in Higher Education, this section delves into valuable approaches for fostering critical thinking within the field of literature. To a greater extent, teachers operate within certain constraints as they are not "free agents," and their teaching conditions are shaped by both the specific context in which teaching is conducted and the academic policies of each university [15]. In literary studies, three essential practices stand out: the proficiency to read and comprehend literary texts, the capability to interpret these texts within their broader context, and the aptitude to question and critique their wider implications and significance [16]. On top of that, emphasizing the research-teaching nexus is crucial, as it encourages both educators and students to foster an environment of critical inquiry [17]. Another vital aspect of this engaged practice is promoting pedagogical constructive methods to adopt a neutral ideological perspective, facilitating the growth of students' critical thinking skills [18].

One approach teachers can employ to assist students in overcoming challenges with critical thinking is the cognitive apprenticeship method. In tackling this, the initial step involves devising skill-specific learning methods to enhance students' capabilities [19]. For instance, if a student struggles to engage in class discussions due to a lack of confidence, an initial one-to-one approach may be suitable. To be more precise, recognizing that students who refrain from participating in seminar discussions during the initial weeks may face continued difficulties, a teacher could foster a sense of belonging by conducting private discussions. As a result, if students feel comfortable sharing their thoughts privately, this interaction may empower them to participate in future discussions and enhance their critical thinking abilities. Another strategy involves leveraging process-based theories that emphasize experience, critical analysis, and subsequent actions based on reflection. These theories posit that true learning, or knowledge integration, occurs through action or "reflective practice." However, as emphasized earlier, the dynamics of learning and teaching are multifaceted. Hence, the various learning theories discussed here

offer diverse perspectives on how teachers should approach the teaching-learning context, providing valuable insights that should be considered.

Several studies assert that the cultivation of students' critical thinking skills is paramount, as it equips them to navigate both their academic environment and personal challenges effectively [20]. As a result, there is a crucial need to support students in honing their capacity for critical thinking. An inherent challenge in promoting this type of thinking lies in the adept analysis and evaluation of sources, considering their social and historical implications. Within the framework of signature pedagogies, involving students directly in research projects becomes imperative for fostering the collaborative creation of new knowledge [21]. Therefore, teachers must grasp the objectives of their disciplines to successfully instill critical thinking in students through the integration of research and teaching. A discussion-based approach to teaching and learning emerges as one of the most effective strategies for nurturing critical thinking skills in students. The suggested teaching strategies explored in this context include creating a conducive and relaxed learning environment, underscoring the value of group and collaborative work, aiding students in connecting ideas and identifying key elements within texts, and fostering an awareness of the diverse perspectives inherent in literary studies in particular and life in general.

4 Ethical Dilemmas in Critical Thinking Practices

As teachers strive to enhance their students' critical thinking abilities, they inevitably grapple with ethical considerations and values, confronting dilemmas where optimal resolutions are inherently subjective. Numerous studies within Higher Education underscore the importance of introducing challenges to encourage students to venture beyond their comfort zones, fostering an environment that wards off boredom and stimulates learning. However, the limited information teachers typically possess about their students' personal circumstances, which may impact their readiness and engagement, necessitates a cautious approach. Teachers must avoid actions that could compromise their students' mental well-being or disrupt the supportive atmosphere that contributes to a sense of belonging and tranquility, ultimately benefiting the learning process. In essence, prioritizing students' well-being and safety should remain a constant consideration for teachers [22].

Addressing the ethical challenges inherent in balancing the promotion of critical thinking practices with the well-being of students, and drawing insights from prevailing trends in UK Higher Education, the ethical dimension has gained considerable prominence. Current evaluations of educational practices often view them through a moral and ethical lens [23]. Notably, values emphasized in the UK Professional Standards Framework, such as respecting diversity, promoting participation, and ensuring equality, highlight the ethical considerations in education [24]. Other values integral to this framework encompass integrity, respect, and care. However, even with established institutional standards, navigating student learning proves

intricate, involving a multitude of complex moral dilemmas. The intricacy stems from the inherent ethical implications present in the majority of teaching decisions, given that they entail a sense of responsibility towards other individuals [25]. For this reason, teachers grapple with numerous ethical dilemmas as an integral aspect of their daily teaching practice [26].

A dilemma manifests as a conflict with multiple potential resolutions, each presenting both advantages and disadvantages. According to some studies, teachers face a challenge wherein increasing the level of difficulty in coursework may induce stress for students who juggle multiple commitments, potentially hindering their ability to prioritize other courses or tasks. In this context, some teachers may opt to maintain higher expectations despite being aware of the potential negative impact on students' anxiety, choosing not to lower their standards. Conversely, other teachers might decide to reduce the challenge's scope, recognizing that students may need to prioritize other responsibilities [27]. In both scenarios, accurately gauging the complete impact of teachers' decisions on their students proves challenging when considering the potential outcomes of alternative actions. Nevertheless, providing teachers with opportunities to consider complex situations from various perspectives holds the potential to improve and enhance ethical choices.

While highlighting the importance of maximizing challenge and stimulating students for the development of critical thinking, it is crucial to prioritize care and nurturing within the teaching and learning context. In navigating moral dilemmas of this nature, teachers can employ strategies such as discussing these issues with colleagues, recognizing the multitude of factors at play, and placing trust in institutional structures that establish procedures to prevent harmful situations for both students and teachers [28]. Even though teachers may not always fully grasp the moral consequences of their actions and practices, they regularly confront numerous dilemmas in managing their students' learning processes. Therefore, when striving to enhance challenge to promote teaching that cultivates students' critical thinking, teachers should be mindful of the potential negative consequences these challenges may pose to students, such as an increase in stress levels. This underscores the importance of adopting an ethics of care and prioritizing the well-being of students.

5 Recommendations

In response to the imperative of nurturing critical thinking within Higher Education, educators are urged to diversify teaching strategies, embracing a reflective approach that fosters collaboration and inclusivity. Ethical considerations, aligned with transparent assessment practices, should underpin teaching methodologies. Additionally, promoting a research-teaching nexus and creating inclusive environments that respect diversity are essential. Below are some recommendations aiming for a comprehensive and effective approach to cultivating critical thinking:

- **Embrace Diverse Teaching Strategies:** Educators should diversify teaching methods within literary studies to cater to varied learning styles and multiple intelligences. Integrating approaches such as small group activities,

technology-enhanced learning, and open-ended discussions can stimulate critical thinking by accommodating different perspectives and fostering a collaborative learning environment.

- **Promote a Reflective Teaching Approach:** Encourage educators to adopt a critically reflective teaching approach. This involves continuous self-assessment, collaboration with students, and an emphasis on creating an inclusive and respectful classroom environment. Reflective teaching enhances the co-creation of knowledge and empowers students to develop their individual critical thinking capacities.
- **Integrate Ethical Considerations in Teaching Practices:** Acknowledge and address ethical dilemmas inherent in challenging students while prioritizing their well-being. Faculty members should engage in discussions with colleagues, consider multiple viewpoints, and trust institutional structures to ensure that the pursuit of critical thinking aligns with ethical standards, respecting diversity and promoting equality.
- **Align Assessment with Learning Outcomes:** Align assessment practices with learning outcomes to reinforce the integration of critical thinking into the learning process. Assessment tasks should be carefully designed to evaluate students' analytical and critical competencies, providing reliable and transparent feedback that informs their understanding of expectations and areas for improvement.
- **Foster a Research-Teaching Nexus:** Encourage the integration of research and teaching in literary studies. Faculty members should design curricula that involve students in the research process, promoting a culture of critical inquiry. By intertwining research and teaching, students gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter, enhancing their critical thinking skills and analytical capabilities.
- **Create Inclusive Learning Environments:** Design learning environments that prioritize inclusivity and respect diversity. Literary studies inherently offer opportunities to explore various perspectives, and educators should leverage this by promoting discussions that highlight the diversity of viewpoints. This inclusive approach contributes to a more comprehensive and nuanced development of critical thinking skills.
- **Provide Professional Development Opportunities:** Institutions should invest in professional development opportunities for faculty members, equipping them with the necessary pedagogical tools and ethical frameworks to effectively nurture critical thinking. Workshops, seminars, and collaborative platforms can facilitate knowledge exchange and the implementation of innovative teaching practices.

By implementing these recommendations, educational institutions can cultivate a robust culture of critical thinking within Higher Education, empowering students to navigate the complexities of literary studies and beyond, and contributing to the broader goal of developing thoughtful, engaged citizens.

6 Conclusion

In most educational settings, encouraging students to engage in critical thinking practices and designing teaching methodologies that allow them to do so is fundamental for their intellectual and personal growth. This requires identifying within the educational process the components that influence the context in which students learn as well as the integration of suitable activities and goals, such as diverse teaching strategies and constructive modalities of assessment. Moreover, approaches that encourage students to engage in critical thinking, such as the ability to thoroughly analyse and evaluate texts in connection to their larger context, as well as opportunities for students to experience a sense of belonging in the classroom, must be fostered. Likewise, the ethical implications that are entwined in the process of critical thinking must be evaluated, such as the importance of motivating students by increasing challenge while maintaining a comfortable environment that nurtures students' well-being. It is crucial that both students and teachers enhance their ability to see things from different perspectives and to connect the teaching and learning processes in the classroom to their broader significance by applying critical thinking to other aspects of their lives. In conclusion, this exploration into the principles, practices, and ethical considerations surrounding the cultivation of critical thinking in Higher Education underscores the intricate web connecting teaching, learning, and the development of analytical capacities. The recommendations presented provide a roadmap for educators and institutions to navigate this complex terrain. By embracing diverse teaching strategies, fostering a reflective teaching approach, and integrating ethical considerations, educators can create environments conducive to the development of critical thinking skills. Aligning assessment practices with learning outcomes reinforces the integration of critical thinking into the educational fabric, while promoting a research-teaching nexus adds depth and relevance to the learning experience. The call for inclusive environments and continuous professional development further emphasizes the need for a holistic approach that respects diversity and adapts to evolving educational landscapes. As we chart the course forward, it becomes evident that nurturing critical thinking in Higher Education is not merely a pedagogical pursuit; it is a commitment to empowering students as thoughtful, engaged contributors to a complex and interconnected world.

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